

THE IMPORTANCE OF GREENING IN BAKU CITY

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Abstract. *Climate change is one of the key global concerns in the modern era, and Azerbaijan has not remained unaffected by its impacts. In this context, the declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Solidarity for a Green World" by President Ilham Aliyev holds strategic significance in the country's environmental policy. Among Azerbaijan's socio-economic development priorities until 2030, actions aimed at ensuring a "Clean Environment and Green Growth" are focused on preserving ecological balance. In this framework, hosting COP29 in Azerbaijan is an indication of the country's active participation in global ecological initiatives.*

Within the framework of modern urban planning and ecological management, parks, boulevards, and other green spaces are being developed in both regular and free styles. The ecological compatibility of the plant species used in the greening process should be considered as the main criterion, and scientific approaches should be followed in the selection of exotic tree and shrub species that can adapt to the climate, alongside local flora. Consequently, the greening policy should serve not only aesthetic and functional purposes but also focus on fundamental goals such as preserving ecological balance, ensuring that the population lives in a healthy environment, and enhancing the overall quality of life.

Keywords: *Climate, global, change, greening, green world.*

One of the global issues concerning the world today is climate change. Climate change and its impact on living organisms are increasingly worrying the international community. Our country has not remained unaffected by global climate changes either.

Sectors such as agriculture, water resources, energy, forestry, tourism, healthcare, and coastal areas in Azerbaijan are particularly vulnerable to climate change. To raise awareness about this issue and strengthen international solidarity, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, signed a decree on December 25, 2023, declaring 2024 as the “Year of Solidarity for a Green World.” This decree once again demonstrates that Azerbaijan is among the first countries to join global initiatives. Furthermore, by declaring 2024 as the “Year of Solidarity for a Green World,” our head of state signals that activities in this field will be expanded throughout the year, and efforts to protect the environment will significantly intensify.

One of Azerbaijan’s five national priorities for socio-economic development until 2030 is to become a “Country of Clean Environment and Green Growth.” In line with this priority, efforts are being made to improve environmental health, restore and expand green spaces, and ensure the efficient use of water resources and sustainable energy sources. The unanimous decision to hold the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties (COP 29) to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change in Azerbaijan is a clear indication of the great respect and trust the international community has for our country. It also highlights Azerbaijan’s valuable contributions to environmental protection and climate change mitigation at national, regional, and global levels.

Parks, gardens, boulevards, and squares in Baku serve as key places for people to relax and stroll. These areas improve living conditions and enhance the architectural appearance of the city. Therefore, urban landscaping projects should be planned so that the distance between these green areas and residential buildings does not exceed 1–1.5 km.

Due to environmental conditions, it is recommended to use evergreen coniferous and broadleaf plants in the landscaping of Baku, as they provide year-round sanitary, hygienic, and health benefits. Environmental factors play a crucial role in the normal growth and development of plants. The most important factors include water availability, drought resistance, tolerance to heat, frost, soil alkalinity, acidity, salinity, and humidity. Based on Baku’s soil-climatic conditions and ecological factors, the following tree and shrub species are recommended for greening: true pistachio, Palestine pistachio, evergreen cypress, common olive, various pine species, majestic laurel, holm oak, willow, Japanese pagoda tree, and others [2, p.115].

The greening of residential areas in Azerbaijan has been practiced since ancient times. Over the centuries, various local landscaping styles have been developed. For example, willows were traditionally planted along irrigation canals and ponds, white mulberry trees were placed in front of houses, while walnut and plane trees were commonly found at road intersections. Every tree and shrub planted for greening purposes not only beautifies and improves the environment but also serves multiple other functions in urban planning and ecological balance.

The objectives of greening and its significance can be summarized as follows: greening enhances the aesthetic appeal of an area, protects it from various negative factors (such as wind and dust), creates healthier living and working conditions, and facilitates recreational activities. Planted trees and shrubs provide additional resources, strengthen sandy and loose soils, stabilize riverbanks and canals, and help retain soil moisture.

In the modern era, extensive efforts are being made to protect the environment and prevent ecological imbalance. Greening plays a crucial role in air purification, mitigating the harmful effects of solar radiation, and meeting the aesthetic and cultural needs of the population. The foundation of these efforts is the establishment of new parks, boulevards, and recreational zones.

The first greening efforts in Absheron date back to the 18th–19th centuries. During this period, individuals, including wealthy landowners and merchants, imported decorative and fruit trees from other countries to adorn their gardens and courtyards. At the beginning of the 20th century, Baku’s green areas were extremely limited—only 20.26 hectares in total, with just 0.5 hectares of public greenery per capita. The harsh climatic and soil conditions of Absheron and Baku, including saline soils, strong winds, and limited irrigation water, posed significant challenges for establishing new parks and green spaces. The process of urban development, beautification, and greening in Baku officially began in 1934. After World War II, greening efforts in Baku and Absheron accelerated. A crucial milestone was reached in 1971 when National Leader Heydar Aliyev issued a decree on "Measures for Greening Baku and the Absheron Peninsula." Greening was declared a nationwide task, resulting in the establishment of 2,520 hectares of green spaces between 1971 and 1975. Later, in 2009, under the decree of President Ilham Aliyev, three million tree seedlings were planted in the Absheron region.

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Parks, gardens, and other green spaces can be created in either regular (geometric) or free (naturalistic) styles. In regular-style landscaping, paths, alleys, tree lines, flower beds, and hedges are arranged symmetrically. These elements can be circular, oval, or rectangular. In contrast, free-style landscaping features more natural, asymmetrical plant placement. Typically, streets, gardens, and boulevards are designed in a regular style, whereas larger parks often follow a free-style layout. Nowadays, a combination of these styles, known as the mixed style, is widely applied. A mixed-style park might have a structured entrance area while the relaxation zones follow a more naturalistic design.

Green areas typically include the following elements:

Dense tree or shrub plantations

Groups of trees and shrubs

Solitary trees and shrubs

Avenues and alleys

Green tunnels

Green hedges, borders, and living fences

Lawns

Flower beds and ornamental foliage plants

When implementing greening projects, efforts should be made to create decorative landscapes that bloom throughout most of the year. This requires planting a variety of trees and shrubs that flower in different seasons. To maintain year-round aesthetics, deciduous plants should be complemented with evergreen and coniferous species. Generally, 8–10 tree and shrub species should form the primary greenery, while additional plants should be used for decorative purposes.

The ecological and biological characteristics of plants must also be considered when selecting species for green spaces. For instance, drought-resistant plants should not be placed in the same area as moisture-demanding plants. Exotic (non-native) species should be planted in small groups or as solitary specimens in prominent locations.

Human health and well-being are closely linked to the surrounding environment. Environmental degradation, including soil, water, and air pollution, as well as reduced oxygen levels, negatively affects public health. The increasing number of radio and television stations, the widespread use of electrical appliances, and industrial noise pollution further contribute to environmental challenges in large cities.

One of the key measures for improving and preserving the environment is protecting plant life, caring for forests, and expanding green spaces. The role of greenery in human health is irreplaceable. Forests and green areas enrich the atmosphere with oxygen. The renowned Russian physiologist K.A. Timiryazev referred to green vegetation as the “source of life” and stated that one hectare of forest supplies enough oxygen for 30 people. Additionally, green spaces filter harmful gases from the air, reducing the concentration of toxic substances by five times and decreasing the number of airborne disease-causing microorganisms by a factor of eight. A single hectare of green forest absorbs 24 kg of carbon dioxide per day—equivalent to the amount exhaled by 500 people.

According to sanitation and hygiene standards, industrial cities with populations exceeding 300,000 should allocate 155–160 hectares of green space per 100 people. Therefore, preserving existing forests, expanding forested areas, and increasing urban greenery are matters of national importance.

On the Absheron Peninsula, intensive human activity has led to vegetation degradation

and worsening ecological conditions. As a result, the issue of restoring a healthy ecological environment is becoming increasingly urgent. Studies by botanical institutions suggest that the introduction of various tree and shrub species can be beneficial for large-scale urban greening projects. The adaptation of introduced species to harsh environmental conditions, their potential use for greening, tolerance to extreme temperatures, growth rhythm, reproduction characteristics, and overall development should be carefully assessed. Absheron, with its dry subtropical climate, industrial infrastructure, and limited natural vegetation, requires a well-researched approach to greening. The scientific study of the bio-ecological properties of tree and shrub species that can withstand local conditions is one of the primary tasks in the region's environmental improvement efforts.

The vegetation of the Absheron Peninsula is characterized by a semi-desert landscape, with sparse presence of wild thyme, sorrel, and ephemeral formations. The flora of the Absheron Peninsula is distinguished by its species diversity. There are 148 species in the wild, including 105 species cultivated in agriculture, with more than 69% of them being annual and biennial plants. [7, p.105]. According to A.A. Grossheim, based on growth conditions, the plant cover of Absheron is divided into three main groups:

Psammophyte plants of the coastal sand strip, plants of humid and dry sandy soils.

Xerophytic plants found in the flat and hilly areas of Absheron. This group includes plants growing on sandy mounds, clay and clayey soils, rocky soils, and sandy and sandy-clay plains.

Halophytic plants that spread in saline and saline-affected soils [5, p.78].

A large number of ephemeral plant species are distributed across the Absheron Peninsula. The abundance of ephemeral plants here is related to the climate regime. In this region, certain correspondences between temperature and humidity conditions provide favorable conditions for their growth. The seasonal development regime of plants in Absheron is clearly reflected. Ephemeral plants and ephemeroïds, which are the builders of semi-deserts, begin to sprout in autumn (after rainfall), remain green throughout the winter and spring, and dry out by May as they complete their growth cycle. Thus, the ephemeral semi-deserts of Absheron have a savanna-like character in winter [9, p.45].

In the ephemeral communities of wild thyme and blackthorn, ephemeral herbs dry out and burn in the summer, but small bushes, wild thyme, blackthorn, calligonum, and other perennial herbs continue their vegetation even in the hot summer and flower and seed in the fall. Rocky, gravelly, and other open areas have fewer plants. Shrubs grow in the crevices of large rocks. These include species like Georgian ninebark, Pallas's honeysuckle, Gantəpər blackberry, Russian gooseberry, yulgun species, small cherry, and many others. The seasonal development of plants in Absheron is a remarkable feature that should be considered when conducting introduction work. The natural tree and shrub species of Absheron include 22 species across 13 genera from 8 families [6, p.159].

The role of ecological factors in the normal development and growth of plants is significant. The most important of these factors include water regime, drought resistance, tolerance to heat, frost, soil alkalinity, acidity, salinity, and moisture resistance. Based on the compatibility with the soil and climate conditions and the ecological needs of the area, the following tree and shrub species are recommended for afforestation: true pistachio, Palestinian pistachio, evergreen cypress, common olive, pine species (Aleppo pine, Eldar pine), magnificent laurel, oak, weeping willow, Japanese sophora, and others [3, p.52].

As a result of the creation of new green spaces, parks, and avenues in Absheron and Baku, the area of greenery has reached 12 thousand hectares. The species composition of these green areas has been enriched. The Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan has started forest planting along the Baku-Gilazi highway. Additionally, the establishment of new parks and gardens continues in Baku and Sumgayit. These measures will lead to the expansion of greenery in Absheron in the coming years. These activities should be considered as positive steps for maintaining ecological stability and improving the environmental health of the region.

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